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Secure Deployment of Smart Meters

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a security-focused approach to the initialization and secure installation of smart meters compliant with the DLMS (Device Language Message Specification) standard. First, a systematic cybersecurity risk analysis is conducted to identify potential threats and vulnerabilities in the smart meter deployment process. Based on this analysis, three approaches to secure meter initialization are proposed: initialization by a technician during installation, initialization within a secure facility of the Distribution System Operator (DSO), and initialization performed directly by the manufacturer. These approaches are compared in terms of cybersecurity, operational practicality, and the required exchange of sensitive information between the manufacturer and the DSO. The results indicate that certain variants can minimize or entirely eliminate the transfer of sensitive data while maintaining compliance with the DLMS standard, thereby enhancing overall system resilience and trustworthiness. Finally, the proposed approaches are validated in a real DSO environment.

1 | Introduction

The rapid digitalization of distribution networks has led to unprecedented reliance on smart metering technologies, particularly those built on the DLMS/COSEM standard (device language message specification/companion specification for energy metering). While DLMS already provides a comprehensive framework for authentication, encryption, and secure data exchange, one essential part of the metering lifecycle remains insufficiently specified: the secure deployment and initialization of smart meters (SMs) before their first authenticated communication with the head-end system (HES).

Before any SM can join the advanced metering infrastructure (AMI) as a trusted entity, several critical security operations must take place: certificate provisioning, key generation, and secure activation of the remote communication. Yet, practical implementations differ significantly across manufacturers, dis-

tribution system operators (DSO), and countries, resulting in a gap between what DLMS secures during operation and what DSO must secure during device roll-out. This gap becomes even more pronounced under modern regulatory requirements (e.g., EU Cybersecurity Act [1], NIS2 [2]), which mandate verifiable protection of confidentiality, integrity, and identity throughout the entire lifecycle.

Therefore, before discussing operational security, there is a need to clarify how SMs should be securely prepared, who performs each step, and how trust is established between the manufacturer, distributor, and the SM itself. This article addresses precisely that challenge. Building on a structured cybersecurity threat analysis, of which only the essential foundations and the most relevant threat categories are included here, we define the security context that motivates the proposed solutions. The three proposed variants in this work are technician-based initialization, Metrolab-based initialization, and manufacturer-

Abbreviations: AMI, Advanced metering infrastructure; DLMS, Device language message specification; DSO, Distribution system operator; HES, Head-end system; MMD, Manufacturer of measuring devices; SM, Smart meter.

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based initialization. Each variant demonstrates different balances between practicality, security assurance, and organizational trust distribution. In the final part of the article, all variants are compared, highlighting their advantages, limitations, and operational implications. The main motivation is to provide a standardized, DLMS-compliant blueprint that closes the pre-deployment security gap and strengthens the overall trustworthiness of AMI infrastructures.

Secure initialization is further complicated by the fact that it spans across multiple organizational domains: manufacturing, logistics, field installation, and the DSO's central infrastructure. Each domain introduces its own constraints, from handling factory-loaded keys to relying on temporary roles or local interfaces during installation. If these steps are not coordinated and consistently secured, they can introduce weaknesses that persist throughout the meter's lifetime. This makes the initialization phase a critical security boundary with long-term impact on meter identity and trustworthiness.

1.1 | Related Articles

Many studies examine cybersecurity challenges in AMI, yet most focus on operational communication phases rather than on the secure initialization and deployment of SMs. Table 1 provides an overview of related works and organizes them into thematic groups. While the table reflects a wide range of research, it also highlights a clear imbalance: the early lifecycle stages of SMs, where trust anchors are established, remain comparatively underexplored. This is significant because weaknesses introduced during deployment may persist for years, regardless of how advanced the operational security mechanisms eventually become.

Another important observation from Table 1 is that many studies address only isolated components of the AMI ecosystem, such as cryptographic algorithms, protocol efficiencies, or anomaly detection mechanisms, without considering how these components depend on the initial provisioning state of the SM. As a result, even comprehensive works often implicitly assume that the SM has already been rolled-out securely, with correct certificates, keys, and access roles in place. In practice, however, improper initialization is a frequent source of configuration drift [28], insecure defaults, and field-operational failures.

Research in the *TH* (*threat landscape and resilience frameworks*) group (e.g., [12, 17, 21]) provides taxonomies of cyber threats and systematic risk assessments for AMI and cyber-physical energy systems. These works consistently identify the deployment phase as a point where trust and authenticity may be weakest, but they do not prescribe concrete, DLMS-compliant initialization procedures.

The *DV* (*DLMS/COSEM validation and standards conformance*) group (e.g., [7]) demonstrates that insecure defaults, inconsistent DLMS implementations, and undocumented device behaviors often originate from inadequate or non-standardized provision-

ing processes. This reinforces the need for unified initialization workflows.

Work in the *PR* (*privacy, aggregation and verifiable billing*) and *KM* (*provisioning, lifecycle and key management*) groups (e.g., [11, 14, 23]) focuses on data privacy, key-management strategies, and end-to-end protection of metering data. However, these approaches generally assume that the SM is already equipped with trusted credentials.

The *PQ* (*post-quantum and lightweight cryptography*) and *CF* (*tooling, automation and secure configuration*) groups (e.g., [22, 27]) highlight requirements such as post-quantum readiness, automated configuration pipelines, and secure CI/CD processes for AMI roll-outs. These works point to a growing need for robust certificate lifecycles and structured provisioning but stop short of comparing practical initialization variants.

Finally, *IM* (*implementation and communication studies*) studies (e.g., [6, 19]) provide empirical insights into communication behavior, channel vulnerabilities, and simulated test environments. Although valuable for understanding operational risks, they do not address the foundational problem of secure onboarding of new meters.

In summary, while Table 1 shows extensive research on AMI security, privacy, and DLMS protocol robustness, none provide a systematic comparison of deployment initialization workflows. This article addresses that gap by analyzing and contrasting three practical, DLMS-compliant initialization variants and evaluating their trust assumptions, security properties, and operational implications.

2 | Background

The device language message specification (DLMS), together with its companion specification for energy metering (COSEM), forms the foundation of the IEC 62056 series of standards, widely adopted for data exchange in smart metering and smart grid applications. DLMS/COSEM defines a standardized, interoperable, and scalable framework enabling secure communication between metering devices and DSO's management systems. In recent years, the increasing digitalization of the energy sector has led to heightened attention to cybersecurity, driven by both technological needs and regulatory mandates. Legislative instruments such as the EU Cybersecurity Act and the NIS2 Directive, along with sector-specific standards, impose stringent requirements on data confidentiality, integrity, authentication, and key management to safeguard critical energy infrastructures and ensure the reliability of smart grid operations. The following subsections provide a more detailed overview of DLMS/COSEM principles and summarize the key cybersecurity legislation and requirements relevant to smart grid environments.

2.1 | The DLMS Standard

The DLMS is an international standard that defines how data is exchanged between smart meters and other systems in the

TABLE 1 | Related articles.

No.	Authors	Year	Group	DLMS	Short description
[3]	R. Mahmud et al.	2015	TH	×	Early survey on metering infra threats and data-management challenges.
[4]	O. Ur-Rehman et al.	2015	TH	×	Survey of smart meter security threats and corresponding countermeasures.
[5]	P. Ganguly et al.	2016	KM	×	Field-analysis of meter anomalies and privacy/measurement impacts.
[6]	M. S. Kemal and R. L. Olsen	2016	IM	✓	Empirical vulnerability/attack experiments on AMI communication channels.
[7]	H. Mendes et al.	2018	DV	✓	Validation/testbed that reveals DLMS implementation deviations and insecure defaults.
[8]	S. Tweneboah-Koduah et al.	2018	CF	×	Chapter covering deployment tooling, testing and automated validation concepts.
[9]	L. Wei et al.	2018	TH	×	Review of cyber-physical attacks and mitigations in AMI contexts.
[10]	A. Brito et al.	2019	KM	×	Survey of cloud/fog-based approaches and their security implications for AMI lifecycle.
[11]	A. Ghosal and M. Conti	2019	TH	×	Comprehensive survey of key-management designs and trade-offs for AMI.
[12]	S. Pealy and M. A. Matin	2020	TH	×	Survey of AMI threats, attacks and high-level countermeasures.
[13]	G. S. Wagh and S. Mishra	2020	PR	×	Privacy-preserving framework integrating billing and resilience.
[14]	G. Bendiab et al.	2020	PR	×	Classic privacy-preserving aggregation techniques for smart-meter data.
[15]	R. Díaz et al.	2020	TH	×	Practical analysis of meter vulnerabilities and detection/mitigation techniques.
[16]	P. Shanmukesh et al.	2021	CF	✓	DLMS/COSEM secure communication framework for next-generation AMI.
[17]	H. Vallant et al.	2021	KM	×	Threat modelling methods and systematic risk assessment applicable to AMI/CPES.
[18]	I. Zografopoulos et al.	2021	KM	×	Threat-modeling and system-level risk assessment for CPES / AMI.
[19]	Z. Zhu et al.	2022	IM	×	Simulated smart meter model for testing electricity data acquisition systems.
[20]	V. Costa et al.	2022	PR	×	Ledger-based billing integrity and auditability for meter readings.
[21]	J. Ding et al.	2022	IM	×	Survey of smart-grid cyber threats, taxonomy, and mitigation approaches.
[22]	C. S. Sandhya et al.	2022	CF	×	Approaches to secure CI/CD and configuration automation for IoT/AMI roll-outs.
[23]	M. Ghiasi et al.	2023	PR	×	Lightweight homomorphic schemes enabling private aggregation for billing.
[24]	D. Shankar et al.	2024	KM	✓	Describes compliance/test procedures for meter cybersecurity (provisioning and validation).
[25]	M. K. Gupta et al.	2024	TH	✓	Recent work on anomaly detection and resilience models for smart-grid telemetry.
[26]	K. Salomón et al.	2025	PQ	×	PLC-based self-diagnostic AMI study in Spanish low-voltage networks.
[27]	J. Jabłoński and R. Dylewski	2025	PQ	×	Design and analysis of PQC approaches for smart-meter authentication and integrity.

DLMS column: Indicates whether the study employs the DLMS standard (✓ = yes, × = no). **Group legend:** TH = threat landscape and resilience frameworks; DV = DLMS/COSEM validation and standards conformance; PQ = post-quantum and lightweight cryptography; PR = privacy, aggregation and verifiable billing; KM = provisioning, lifecycle and key management; CF = tooling, automation and secure configuration; IM = implementation and communication studies.

TABLE 2 | Example DLMS register object.

Attr.	Name	Value	Description
1	Logical name	1.0.52.7.0.255	L2 voltage (instantaneous)
2	Value	2412	Raw measured value
3	Scaler & unit	S: -1, U: 35	Voltage (35)

field of energy management and automation. Although its specification is extensive and technically detailed, understanding a few fundamental principles helps clarify how DLMS operates in practice.

DLMS communication is structured according to the OSI/ISO reference model, focusing primarily on layers 4 to 7. This approach ensures interoperability across a wide range of communication technologies. As a result, DLMS can be implemented over both wired media (such as RS-485, Ethernet, and M-Bus) and wireless technologies (including LTE, NB-IoT, wireless M-Bus, and GPRS). This flexibility makes DLMS one of the most widely adopted standards for smart metering worldwide.

The DLMS standard is typically divided into two main components:

1. DLMS/COSEM Communication Framework: Described in the DLMS Green Book [29], this part defines the communication mechanisms, data exchange procedures, and built-in security features such as authentication and encryption.
2. COSEM Object Model and OBIS System: Documented in the DLMS Blue Book [30], this part specifies the COSEM, which defines the data model used in meters, and the object identification system (OBIS), which assigns unique identifiers to each measurable quantity or function within the device.

2.1.1 | DLMS Basics

In a DLMS-enabled smart meter, the internal data is organized into COSEM objects. Each object represents a specific functionality or data point that can be accessed remotely. Typical examples include objects representing instantaneous values (such as voltage, current, and power), profile objects that store historical data over time, and billing objects used for tariff management and consumption calculation. Additionally, meters contain configuration and control objects that manage communication parameters, access rights, and security settings.

An example of a DLMS register object, one of the most common object types used to represent measured quantities, is shown in Table 2. Each object includes a logical name, which serves as its unique identifier, along with attributes that describe its current value, unit, and scaling factor. For instance, a register object measuring voltage on phase L2 might store a raw value of 2412, with a scaler of -1 and a unit code corresponding to volts (V).

When these components are combined, the resulting measured value is 241.2 V.

Through this object-oriented approach, DLMS ensures high scalability and interoperability, enabling DSO to integrate smart meters, data concentrators, and head-end systems from different manufacturers seamlessly. Moreover, the DLMS/COSEM model supports future-proof extensions, allowing new measurement types, security features, and data access methods to be added without disrupting existing systems.

2.1.2 | DLMS Cybersecurity

Security is a fundamental component of the DLMS/COSEM standard, ensuring that smart metering systems can operate safely within increasingly interconnected and critical infrastructures such as modern smart grids. The standard defines multiple mechanisms for authentication, data confidentiality, and integrity protection, aiming to prevent unauthorized access, tampering, or data interception during communication between clients (e.g., head-end systems) and servers (e.g., meters or concentrators).

2.1.2.1 | Authentication Mechanisms. Authentication in DLMS occurs during the initial phase of communication. Before any data object can be accessed, the client must successfully authenticate with the server. The standard defines eight authentication levels, grouped into three main categories based on the degree of protection offered.

1. No Security (Lowest Level): This level provides no authentication and is intended only for public or low-risk access, such as reading general identification data. It should not be used in any environment where security or privacy is a concern.
2. Low-Level Security (LLS): The LLS mechanism uses a pre-shared secret key that is transmitted in plaintext. While it provides minimal access control, it is inherently insecure for remote communication, as the credentials can be intercepted and reused in replay attacks. Consequently, LLS is typically restricted to local maintenance or test environments.
3. High-Level Security (HLS): The HLS framework provides robust protection through a challenge-response mechanism, in which both parties exchange four messages to mutually verify their identities. HLS can be combined with various cryptographic algorithms to generate and verify challenge responses [31]. Supported algorithms include:
 - GMAC (Galois Message Authentication Code) used for message authentication and integrity checking.
 - SHA-256 (Secure Hash Algorithm) for cryptographic hashing and challenge generation.
 - ECDSA (Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm) enabling signature-based authentication without shared secrets.

Earlier algorithms such as MD5 and SHA-1 are also available, but due to known vulnerabilities are deprecated. When ECDSA is employed, the authentication relies entirely on digital certificates and a public key infrastructure (PKI). This approach eliminates the need for pre-shared keys, as both entities validate each other's certificates against a trusted root authority.

TABLE 3 | DLMS security suites [29].

Suite ID	Authenticated encryption	Digital signature	Key agreement	Hash	Key transport	Compression
0	AES-GCM-128	—	—	—	AES-128 key wrap	—
1	AES-GCM-128	ECDSA P-256	ECDH P-256	SHA-256	AES-128 key wrap	V.44
2	AES-GCM-256	ECDSA P-384	ECDH P-384	SHA-384	AES-256 key wrap	V.44
3–15	Reserved for future updates (e.g., post-quantum cryptography)					

2.1.2.2 | Data Protection. Beyond authentication, DLMS ensures ongoing data confidentiality and integrity through encryption and message authentication. These capabilities are defined within the concept of security suites, which specify combinations of cryptographic algorithms and key management procedures.

The advanced encryption standard (AES) is the foundation of all DLMS security suites, used in Galois counter mode (GCM) for authenticated encryption. This mode provides both confidentiality and integrity in a single operation, making it efficient for constrained devices such as smart meters.

DLMS currently defines three security suites (see Table 3):

- Security Suite 0 (SS0): Utilizes AES-GCM-128 with pre-shared symmetric keys. It provides basic protection suitable for systems with limited cryptographic capability but relies on secure key provisioning.
- Security Suite 1 (SS1): Introduces asymmetric key exchange via ECDH P-256, digital signatures using ECDSA P-256, and SHA-256 hashing. This suite offers a strong balance between security and performance, and it is the most widely implemented configuration in modern DLMS systems.
- Security Suite 2 (SS2): Employs stronger cryptographic primitives, including AES-GCM-256, ECDSA P-384, and SHA-384, providing enhanced resistance against quantum-era threats and aligning with emerging NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) recommendations for long-term data protection [32].

All key establishment procedures in SS1 and SS2 use the elliptic curve Diffie–Hellman (ECDH) algorithm to securely derive symmetric session keys. Future DLMS revisions (suites 3–15) are reserved for upcoming cryptographic models and possible post-quantum algorithms.

The security suites also define how protection is applied to each transmitted message. DLMS combines encryption, authentication tags, and frame counters to prevent replay attacks and tampering, ensuring that messages cannot be reused or altered without detection. These mechanisms are especially relevant during the initialization phase, when keys and certificates are first exchanged, and secure handling of early communication is essential for establishing a trusted device state.

2.2 | Cybersecurity Legislation

The security requirements for modern smart metering systems are shaped not only by technical standards such as DLMS/COSEM [29], but also by a broad set of European and national legislative frameworks. As emphasized in [33], regulatory obligations increasingly demand that security be ensured across the entire lifecycle of smart meters (from manufacturing and initialization to long-term operation).

At the European level, the most relevant legal instrument is the NIS2 Directive [2], which significantly strengthens cybersecurity requirements for operators of essential and important entities, including electricity distribution operators. NIS2 mandates comprehensive risk management, secure-by-design principles, incident reporting, supply-chain oversight, and cryptographic safeguards that must remain robust over the multi-decade operational life of AMI devices.

These requirements operate alongside additional union legislation with direct implications for smart meter cybersecurity. The Cybersecurity Act [1] establishes an EU-wide cybersecurity certification framework, enabling the definition of assurance schemes applicable to connected metering devices, communication modules, and backend systems. The upcoming Cyber Resilience Act [34] introduces mandatory cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements, including embedded devices used in smart meters, addressing secure development, vulnerability handling, and lifecycle support. Data protection obligations arising from the GDPR [35] are important given the high resolution of consumption data and its potential to reveal household behavior patterns, requiring data minimization, strong encryption, and privacy-preserving architectures. For the energy domain specifically, the Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944 [36] and its accompanying Network Codes promote interoperability, secure remote operation, and consumer data access rights, all of which depend on trustworthy metering infrastructure. Collectively, these instruments reinforce the necessity of secure roll-out processes, hardware-rooted trust anchors, protected provisioning of keys and certificates, and update mechanisms capable of evolving cryptographic primitives in response to emerging threats.

At the national level, EU member states transpose NIS2 into binding law. In the Czech Republic, key obligations arise from Act 264/2025 on cybersecurity [37] and its implementing regulations, complemented by the sector-specific Decree 359/2020 on electricity metering [38]. Annex 4 of this decree defines minimum technical and cryptographic requirements for AMI

FIGURE 1 | Security initialization data flow diagram.

systems, including authenticated access control, event logging, integrity protection, unique device identifiers, secure firmware updates, and safe handling of cryptographic credentials [33]. Similar emphasis on regulatory compliance can be found in risk-assessment research on AMI infrastructures [12, 17], which stresses that national legislation increasingly demands verifiable, testable, and repeatable security controls.

Finally, regulators and researchers agree on the long-term need for cryptographic agility and preparations for a post-quantum environment. Guidance from ENISA (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity), NIST, and NÚKIB (National Cyber and Information Security Agency) increasingly emphasizes replacing legacy mechanisms such as static symmetric master keys with modern, upgradeable schemes based on ECDH, ECDSA, and AES-256, while ensuring a clear migration path toward quantum-resilient primitives. Recent EU legislation (including NIS2) reinforces these expectations by requiring energy infrastructures to maintain strong, future-proof cryptographic protections throughout the device lifecycle.

In summary, both legislation and the broader research landscape converge on a clear message: secure initialization and deployment are not optional, but legally required foundational steps for any modern AMI roll-out. The initialization variants proposed in this article directly address these expectations by providing DLMS-compliant, auditable, and operationally feasible approaches to establishing trust at the moment of installation.

3 | Risk Analysis

Secure smart meter initialization involves the establishment of trust anchors, cryptographic identities, and access privileges across multiple organizational and technical domains. As illus-

trated in the security diagram in Figure 1, the initialization process crosses several trust boundaries, including manufacturing, laboratory, deployment, and operational environments. Weaknesses introduced at this stage can persist throughout the meter's lifecycle, making deployment a critical security boundary that warrants systematic risk analysis.

To analyze these risks in a structured and repeatable manner, this work applies the STRIDE-LM (spoofing, tampering, repudiation, information disclosure, denial of service, elevation of privilege, and lateral movement) threat model [39]. STRIDE is a well-established threat-modeling framework [40] originally developed by Microsoft to identify security risks across system components, data flows, and trust boundaries. Its extension with lateral movement is particularly relevant for interconnected infrastructures such as smart metering systems, where compromise of one component may enable broader system impact.

The objective of the risk analysis is to identify where threats such as device impersonation, unauthorized configuration, key compromise, or privilege escalation may arise during initialization, and to determine which security controls must be embedded into the deployment workflow. The resulting threat model provides a structured basis for evaluating the initialization variants presented later in the article and for assessing their implications for long-term system security.

The analysis assumes a realistic attacker model that includes compromised communication channels, malicious or misconfigured infrastructure components, and insider threats within organizational boundaries. The goal is not to enumerate all possible attacks, but to identify structural weaknesses in the initialization workflow that could enable long-term compromise of smart metering infrastructure.

3.1 | Security Diagram

Figure 1 presents a consolidated data flow diagram (DFD) capturing the basic data exchanges that occur across the smart metering system. The diagram represents a simplified abstraction derived from practical experience with real DSO infrastructures, existing AMI deployments, and established initialization workflows. It integrates the principal initialization and operational data flows associated with SMs and defines the trusted boundaries among the Manufacturer Zone (L1), the DSO Metrolab Zone (L2), and the Smart Meter Deployment Zone (L3), forming a minimal yet realistic basis for systematic threat modeling.

The SM is depicted in three positions within the diagram, each representing a possible stage of its initialization lifecycle. In Zone L1, the meter is manufactured and provisioned with initial credentials and configuration parameters. It may then be transferred to the DSO Metrolab (via T1) for controlled testing and further initialization in Zone L2. The final position (via T2) is deployment at the customer premises in Zone L3, where the meter becomes an active endpoint of the secure metering infrastructure. Together, these positions represent the complete initialization path from production to field deployment and illustrate the progressive establishment of trust anchors and secure communication. In addition to the meter zones (L1–L3), the DFD defines two upper-tier trust zones responsible for system-wide cryptographic trust.

The RootCA Zone represents the highest trust domain in the architecture. It contains the Root Certificate Authority (RootCA) and its associated secure storage, which protects both the public and private root keys. As depicted in the diagram, the RootCA is responsible for issuing the RootCA certificate to external entities and signing the SubCA certificates that enable downstream certificate hierarchies. No operational metering data flows through this zone, instead it serves as the origin of trust for the entire smart metering ecosystem.

The HES Zone, as represented in the DFD, is modeled as a single logical entity including the DSO's head-end system, the subordinate certificate authority (SubCA), and the associated secure storage components. This abstraction reflects that, from a data flow perspective, all interactions terminating in the HES Zone share a common trust boundary and are treated uniformly in the diagram. However, in a real deployment, the HES environment is typically composed of multiple interconnected subsystems with distinct operational responsibilities. These include the communication server that receives data from meters, a dedicated key management system (KMS) overseeing the secure storage and lifecycle management of cryptographic keys and certificates, several database layers, orchestration and control systems, and downstream analytical engines. Additional components handle data processing, validation, aggregation, and make the resulting information available to market participants such as energy suppliers, regulators, and, where applicable, end customers. Although these components form a distributed technical landscape, their collective functions are represented as a single HES entity in the DFD to maintain clear trust boundaries and communication paths, and because the internal

structure of the HES is not relevant from the smart meter's communication perspective.

The diagram contains seven principal data flows, labeled 1 through 7, each representing a discrete interaction across trust boundaries:

1. **RootCA Certificate Distribution.** The RootCA sends its public certificate to the manufacturer, allowing the manufacturer to embed trusted credentials into the smart meter during production.
2. **Certificate Injection at Manufacturing.** In Zone L1, the manufacturer injects the required certificates into the smart meter, establishing the meter's initial cryptographic identity.
3. **Signing of the SubCA Certificate.** The RootCA signs the SubCA certificate used within the HES Zone, creating the next level of the certificate hierarchy.
4. **Signing of HES and Smart Meter Certificates.** The SubCA signs certificates for both the HES and the smart meters, enabling authenticated and trusted communication once meters are operational.
5. **Encrypted Tunnel for Remote Initialization.** An encrypted tunnel can be established between the smart meter located in the DSO Metrolab and the HES. This tunnel enables the HES to perform the initialization process remotely while the meter remains physically connected in the metrolab environment. In practice, this functions as a mediated local connection, allowing the HES to execute initialization procedures as if the meter were already deployed, while still operating within a controlled and secure environment.
6. **Smart Meter Initialization at the DSO Metrolab.** In Zone L2, the DSO Metrolab performs additional initialization steps, which may include verification, secure parameter loading, or test communication.
7. **Primary Communication Interface Between the HES and the Smart Meter.** This data flow represents the main communication channel used during the meter's operational life. In current Czech deployments, this interface is typically implemented using a mobile connection operating within a private APN¹, although other communication technologies may also be used. The communication itself can operate at three security levels:
 - (a) *Unsecured Communication:* Used only in limited cases, such as very early initialization steps or reading public information from the meter before secure channels are established.
 - (b) *Secured and Encrypted Communication:* The standard mode used for normal operational data exchange, including consumption data, configuration reads, and routine service interactions.
 - (c) *Critical Communication:* A highly protected mode used for operations that may affect system integrity. This includes modifications of critical meter settings, customer disconnection commands, role configuration, and updates to CA certificates.

3.2 | Key Threats Identified by the Analysis

The STRIDE-LM analysis was conducted as a structured, requirement driven threat modeling exercise based on a DFD developed in cooperation with the DSO. A top-down first-level DFD was designed to capture key elements, data flows, and trust boundaries of the smart meter initialization process and subsequently refined for STRIDE-LM-per-element analysis. This approach resulted in a comprehensive and detailed assessment covering a broad set of threats and mitigation measures. For clarity and readability, only the most relevant and representative security threats are summarized below.

Spoofing threats were observed at interfaces where devices or infrastructure components authenticate for the first time during initial commissioning. Without a securely provisioned cryptographic identity, a smart meter may accept invalid or unauthorized certificates or communicate with impersonated head-end components, undermining the authenticity of subsequent secure sessions.

Tampering risks were identified in relation to initialization data, firmware configuration, and cryptographic material handled during production, transport, and laboratory setup. Manipulation at this stage can permanently compromise device integrity and is difficult to detect during later operational phases.

Repudiation threats arise when initialization actions are insufficiently logged or authenticated across organizational boundaries. If provisioning operations, certificate issuance, or configuration changes cannot be reliably attributed to authorized entities, accountability and post-incident analysis become severely limited.

Information disclosure threats were associated with early communication phases that precede activation of full DLMS security mechanisms in practice. Exposure of keys, certificates, or configuration parameters during initialization enables follow-on attacks such as spoofing, privilege escalation, or unauthorized access to other system components.

Denial of service threats were identified both at infrastructure components involved in initialization, such as PKI services and metrology systems, and at the smart meter itself. Disruption of these services can delay deployment, force insecure fallback procedures, or prevent secure commissioning of devices in practice.

Elevation of privilege risks were primarily linked to excessive or persistent privileges assigned to initialization roles. If high-privilege credentials or access rights are retained beyond deployment, they may be exploited to gain unauthorized control during normal operation.

Finally, the analysis highlighted *lateral movement* as a systemic risk following compromise of highly trusted components, including RootCA, SubCA, or initialization environments. Such compromises enable attackers to issue valid credentials or impersonate legitimate entities across multiple security zones, amplifying the impact of a single breach.

TABLE 4 | Threat traceability matrix (STRIDE-LM vs. initialization variants).

Threat	1a	1b	1c	2a	2b	2c	3a	3b
Spoofing	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	~	~	✓
Tampering	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	~	✓	✓
Repudiation	~	✓	~	✓	✓	~	~	✓
Information disclosure	✓	✓	~	✓	✓	~	✓	✓
Denial of service	✓	~	~	✓	✓	~	✓	~
Elevation of privilege	✓	✓	~	✓	✓	~	✓	✓
Lateral movement	~	✓	~	✓	✓	~	✓	✓

Legend: ✓ = structurally mitigated by design; ~ = partially mitigated or implementation dependent; ✗ = structurally exposed during initialization.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that initialization is a decisive phase for long-term system security. The identified threats directly inform the initialization variants presented in the following section and motivate the emphasis on controlled provisioning environments, authenticated communication paths, and strict role separation.

3.3 | Threat Traceability Matrix

To explicitly link the identified STRIDE-LM threat categories to the proposed initialization approaches described in Section 4, Table 4 presents a condensed threat traceability matrix. The matrix maps the dominant threat classes to the individual sub-variants (1a–3b) and summarizes their structural mitigation characteristics during the initialization phase.

The evaluation reflects high-level architectural properties of each variant, including trust distribution, communication channel exposure, and reliance on PKI-based authentication, rather than implementation specific hardening measures. In particular, bridged variants (1b, 2b, 3b) benefit from direct HES control over certificate provisioning, while remote initialization over the primary communication interface (1c, 2c) exhibits increased exposure during early association phases. In Variant 2c, this exposure is partially mitigated by controlled laboratory conditions and subsequent personnel verification, whereas in Variant 1c equivalent assurance depends on field procedures.

The primary weakness of Variant 1c arises from the absence of a cryptographically proved SM identity during the earliest phase of remote association. Until certificate based authentication is completed, the HES cannot fully verify the authenticity of the device. This temporary identity gap also explains the increased exposure to tampering risks in this variant, as configuration steps may initially rely on weaker assurance mechanisms compared to bridged or laboratory based approaches.

For denial of service, the assessment considers exposure to external communication channels during initialization. Variants executed entirely within controlled laboratory or factory networks (e.g., 2a, 2b, 3a) are therefore considered structurally resistant to network-based DoS at this stage, although availability

of backend systems and PKI services remains outside the scope of this architectural evaluation.

With respect to elevation of privilege, the mitigation in all variants is primarily derived from the PKI-based authentication model. Even in scenarios where a default or temporary password is used for initial access, escalation to higher security roles requires possession of valid cryptographic credentials issued within the DSO PKI hierarchy. Consequently, knowledge of an initialization password alone does not enable access to management or security-critical roles without valid PKI credentials.

Several mitigations in the matrix assume correct enforcement of the role-based access model described in Section 5.

4 | Designing Initialization Flow

When designing the initialization flow for secure smart meter deployment, several aspects should be considered as non-mandatory design guidelines informed by practical DSO experience and the preceding risk analysis. The following aspects are considered:

- ensuring safe operation during deployment,
- determining who performs the critical steps,
- deciding on security trust between distributor and manufacturer,
- deciding whether to use uniform passwords for initial initialization,
- determining whether it is necessary to transfer sensitive device information between the manufacturer and the distributor.

All proposed schemes assume the use of asymmetric cryptography, including a public key infrastructure and key exchange based on ECDH. For simplification, the abbreviations manufacturer of measuring devices (MMD), smart meter (SM), and DSO are used throughout. All communication relies exclusively on mechanisms standardized within DLMS and does not deviate from the specification.

At present, Security Suite 2 represents the highest defined security level within DLMS. While it employs AES-GCM-256 and larger elliptic curves (P-384), this does not constitute true post-quantum security [27]. Although AES-256 provides increased resistance against Grover's algorithm in the symmetric setting, the asymmetric primitives used for authentication and key agreement (ECDSA and ECDH) remain vulnerable to Shor's algorithm in a sufficiently capable quantum adversary [41]. Consequently, the proposed initialization schemes rely on classical public-key cryptographic assumptions. In a post-quantum scenario, the asymmetric primitives used for authentication and key establishment would need to be replaced by quantum-resistant alternatives. However, this substitution would affect the underlying cryptographic mechanisms rather than the logical structure of the proposed initialization workflows.

Nevertheless, the architectural separation of trust anchors, certificate management, and role-based security described in this work is independent of specific cryptographic algorithms. The proposed schemes can accommodate future DLMS security suites incorporating post-quantum signature and key encapsulation mechanisms, such as NIST-standardized ML-DSA (CRYSTALS-Dilithium) or SLH-DSA (SPHINCS+) for digital signatures and ML-KEM (CRYSTALS-Kyber) for key establishment, or other approved primitives [42]. Migration to such schemes would primarily affect certificate sizes, key storage requirements, computational overhead, and initialization data volume, while the logical structure of the proposed workflows would remain unchanged.

The individual proposals include additional sub-variants, which primarily differ in the system and connection used for the initialization itself. Figure 2 contains all sub-variants at a high level by showing the communication paths. An overview of the proposals is as follows:

1. **Variation 1 – Technician:** The SM is delivered by the manufacturer directly for installation, but it does not have initialized security settings. During installation at the deployment zone, the technician performs this initialization (using automated programs and scripts).
 - (a) Local Configuration: The SM is configured locally using software that does not communicate with the central system, except for the certificate signing request for the SM.
 - (b) Bridged Configuration: Local access to the SM is tunneled/bridged (e.g., via VPN) through a secure channel directly to the HES central system which performs all steps.
 - (c) Remote Configuration: Configuration is carried out directly over the primary interface (mobile network), which is potentially insecure and unprotected during first initialization phase.
2. **Variation 2 – Metrolab:** The SM is first delivered to a secure DSO facility (Metrolab), where it is initialized, commissioned, and tested prior to deployment. The sub-variants correspond structurally to those defined in Variation 1, but are executed under controlled conditions.
 - (a) Local Configuration: Functionally equivalent to Variation 1a, but executed within a controlled Metrolab environment with physical supervision and centralized audit.
 - (b) Bridged Configuration: Architecturally equivalent to Variation 1b, with the tunnel established from the Metrolab network, reducing exposure to external communication infrastructure.
 - (c) Remote Configuration: Follows the same technical steps as Variation 1c; however, configuration is performed prior to field deployment and can be verified by Metrolab personnel.
3. **Variation 3 – Manufacturer:** The SM is completely initialized by the manufacturer and can be directly deployed as fully secured at the deployment zone.
 - (a) Local Configuration: The manufacturer uses its own MMD SubCA, which is signed by the DSO RootCA certificate.

FIGURE 2 | Comparison of all variants.

(b) Bridged Configuration: The manufacturer bridges the connection, while the HES system performs the configuration.

No remote sub-variant is defined for the Manufacturer variant. In practice, the manufacturer does not typically operate within the DSO communication domain, and direct access to the primary communication infrastructure (e.g., mobile connectivity provisioned for the DSO) cannot be assumed. If such connectivity were technically and contractually established, the initialization steps would correspond to Variant 2c.

4.1 | Common Initialization Scheme

Figure 3 presents the common initialization scheme that serves as the baseline for all subsequently discussed variants. It defines the mandatory communication flows, participating entities, and cryptographic preparations that are shared across all schemes.

The process begins with the DSO establishing the PKI. The DSO creates the RootCA, initializes the required certificates, and signs the subordinate certification authorities. Especially, the HES SubCA is signed by the DSO RootCA. In parallel, for the Variant 3a, the manufacturer's infrastructure is prepared by signing the MMD SubCA. It is assumed that the DSO RootCA is generated and secured prior to the start of the scheme.

Following PKI preparation, the relevant certificates are shared with the manufacturer environment. At a minimum, the DSO RootCA is distributed, HES-related certificates (HES² and HES SubCA) are optional and their inclusion depends on the specific variant. During the SM initialization, the SM imports the required trust anchors. The DSO RootCA is mandatory, while the MMD

SubCA is only imported in Variant 3a. HES certificates remain optional across all variants.

After the SM is provisioned with the firmware and the corresponding certificates, the process reaches the point at which the individual variants begin to diverge. In the common scheme shown in Figure 3, this divergence point is explicitly indicated by the standalone blue rectangle. It represents the transition from the shared initialization steps to variant-specific procedures, in which the subsequent communication flows, trust relationships, and security operations may differ depending on the selected scheme. Once the variant-specific steps are completed, the initialization phase is concluded and normal, fully secured operational communication between the system components can continue.

After the variant-specific steps, a symmetric key agreement between the HES and the SM may be performed, depending on the selected variant. In some variants, this key agreement is part of the common initialization flow, while in others it is executed entirely within the variant-specific procedures. When performed, the key agreement may be repeated multiple times to derive the required set of operational keys. Once key establishment is completed, the initial setup is finalized using encrypted communication.

If the key agreement is incorporated into the variant-specific steps, it may be established only for higher security roles. In such cases, the derived keys are used to enable a secure connection and to support the subsequent generation or derivation of additional keys after the meter has been deployed. This behavior is highly dependent on the specific variant and on the DSO's security architecture and operational policies, and it is therefore optional rather than mandatory.

FIGURE 3 | Common flow for all variants.

FIGURE 4 | Scheme Variant 1 – Technician.

The scheme concludes with fully secured and encrypted operational communication between the HES and the SM. This final state represents the common security baseline upon which all further variant-specific differences are built.

4.2 | Variant 1 – Technician

Figure 4 illustrates the scheme of Variant 1, referred to as the Technician. At the start of the process, the SM contains at least the DSO RootCA and is delivered to the deployment zone, where

a field technician performs the installation. After the technician installs the meter at the customer premises, a SIM card is inserted into the meter, unless this step has already been performed at an earlier stage in accordance with the DSO’s internal processes and policies.

The technician then establishes a connection to the SM via a local interface³ using an authorized access terminal⁴. In order to configure the SIM PIN, access to a dedicated role is required⁵. Once the connection is successfully established, the technician

configures the SIM PIN by writing it to the appropriate object in the meter. After the PIN has been set, the initialization of the security configuration can begin. At this point, the process may diverge depending on how the remaining configuration steps are executed.

The most suitable approach (Variant 1b) is to bridge the local interface and expose it directly to the HES. This ensures that sensitive configuration data remain within the HES and avoids procedural inconsistencies by enabling a fully automated configuration process.

An alternative approach (Variant 1a) is to perform the same configuration steps locally, under the control of an application running on the access terminal. The third option (Variant 1c) uses the primary communication interface, with the HES communicating with the SM in the same manner as during normal operation after deployment (however, at the beginning of the process this communication is not encrypted and may take place over a potentially unsecured channel).

For the variant 1b, the steps are as follows (but overall, the steps are similar/reflected also in the other 2 sub-variants). At the beginning of the initialization, the SM is connected to an access terminal via a local interface. The access terminal then bridges this connection directly to the HES. The entire initialization process is therefore controlled and executed by the HES. The first step consists of uploading the certificates (HES SubCA and HES) into the SM (if not done previously by a different entity). Access to this procedure again requires the use of a specific security role. At this stage, only certificates that can be validated against the root certificate (DSO RootCA) may be imported. From a security perspective, it is therefore not strictly necessary to require a password for accessing the certificate upload objects at this point.

Continuing from the previous step within the same session, methods are invoked to generate a cryptographic key pair directly on the SM. The generated public key is then used to create a Certificate Signing Request (CSR), which is transmitted to the HES and subsequently signed by the certification authority (HES SubCA). The resulting signed certificate (DSO SM) is then imported back into the SM. This certificate can be successfully verified, as it is signed by the HES SubCA, which forms part of the trust chain anchored at the DSO RootCA.

At this stage, the SM contains the root certificate (DSO RootCA), the signing certificate (HES SubCA), the certificate of the central system (DSO HES), and its own device certificate (DSO SM). This certificate set enables authenticated access using the appropriate security role for the final parameter configuration. Authentication is performed using HLS-ECDSA, and an encryption key is subsequently established using the ECDH algorithm. From this point onward, all communication can be encrypted using the negotiated key, allowing the remaining configuration steps to be completed securely.

The finalization phase may include actions such as locking or disabling unnecessary roles, modifying access rights to objects required only during initial setup, generating additional keys or

certificates for remaining roles, and regenerating authentication passwords for selected local roles (e.g., technician or customer). After completion of these steps SM is prepared for normal operation (fully secured and encrypted). Technician should validate once more, if the connectivity to the HES is stable on the primary communication interface.

4.3 | Variant 2 – Metrolab

Variant 2 Metrolab is closely related to Variant 1 and differs primarily in the entity performing the initialization steps. In Variant 1, as illustrated in Figure 4, the initialization is carried out by a DSO Technician at the deployment zone. In Variant 2, this role is transferred to a metrology laboratory (Metrolab). Although the process may still be considered a technician-driven procedure, it is performed by specialized personnel within a controlled laboratory rather than in the field.

All technical steps remain identical to those in Variant 1, however the execution takes place indoors, within a secure zone, and is handled by more experienced professionals using dedicated equipment. A key advantage of this variant is the significantly higher initialization throughput compared to field-based initialization. In addition, the metrolab environment enables comprehensive functional testing of the SMS, including verification of correct consumption measurement, prior to deployment.

Within this variant, the SM can be fully prepared before installation. This includes firmware updates, certificate injection, SIM card installation, configuration of the HES, and registration of the meter to a specific customer. As a result, the on-site technician's tasks are minimized. During field deployment, the technician is only required to physically install the meter, position the antenna, and verify that the meter communicates correctly with the HES.

4.4 | Variant 3 – Manufacturer

The third variant, referred to as the Manufacturer, is illustrated in Figure 5. This variant differs significantly from the first two variants. Notably, the SM can be prepared for immediate deployment without any on-site intervention by a technician or any other entity (e.g., at Metrolab). In this variant, there is also an optional step in which the manufacturer installs the DSO's SIM card into the meter and configures the corresponding PIN and APN parameters. This step is shown separately in the scheme, as it is optional and may alternatively be performed by another authorized entity.

For this variant, two sub-variants are defined: local and bridged. The bridged sub-variant (Variant 3b) operates in the same manner as shown in previous variants. The manufacturer connects the SM to the system via a local interface, and the system is securely connected to the DSO's HES, which performs the initialization of all required security parameters. In practice, this approach may be operationally demanding, as it requires integration of the manufacturer's production environment with the DSO infrastructure and the establishment of a controlled secure communication channel. Architecturally, however, this sub-variant is

FIGURE 5 | Scheme Variant 3 – Manufacturer.

equivalent to the bridged configurations described in Variants 1b and 2b, differing only in the entity executing the initialization procedure.

In the Variant 3a (Local), the meter is prepared by the MMD and is fully ready for deployment, including cybersecurity setup for immediate secure communication. The SM contains all required certificates, including its own certificate, and all necessary encryption and authentication keys can be securely injected during the manufacturing phase.

The local initialization process begins with the injection of the DSO RootCA certificate. The MMD then injects additional certificates, such as the HES SubCA and optionally the HES certificate. This procedure is similar to the other variants, however, this sub-variant introduces one additional certificate. The MMD SubCA certificate is created specifically for the given manufacturer and is signed by the DSO RootCA⁶, as illustrated in Figure 3. The presence of the MMD SubCA enables the manufacturer to generate and sign all required certificates for the smart meter, including the MMD-issued smart meter certificate. Once the meter is fully prepared, a shipment file is generated. This file contains cryptographic material and relevant metadata associated with the meter and is transferred to the DSO via a secure communication channel.⁷

After deployment and installation of the SIM card, the meter can initiate communication with the HES. If not already performed within the MMD, the HES may import its SubCA certificate and its own certificate into the meter at this stage. Once both entities possess all required certificates, the HES can establish a secured association with the meter using HLS-ECDSA, relying on the HES certificate and the MMD-issued smart meter certificate. The use of ECDSA provides mutual cryptographic authentication, ensuring that both parties can reliably verify each other's identities, therefore, from a theoretical standpoint, data encryption is not strictly required at this stage.

At the beginning of this communication phase, the HES generates a new smart meter certificate, which is signed exclusively by the HES SubCA. After successful import of this certificate, the MMD SubCA certificate is removed from the meter's trust store. This step effectively eliminates the MMD from any further trusted communication with the meter. Subsequently, the newly issued certificates are used to perform an ECDH key agreement, allowing the HES and the meter to derive fresh encryption and authentication keys. From this point onward, encrypted communication can be enabled, if it has not already been configured during the manufacturing process.

4.5 | Comparison

The advantages and disadvantages of the individual initialization variants are analyzed in this section in the context of both operational requirements and cybersecurity considerations. The comparison explicitly relates the variants to the deployment aspects defined at the beginning of Section 4 and to the key threat categories identified in the STRIDE-LM analysis in Section 3, highlighting how each variant mitigates specific risks and where trade-offs arise. If a particular observation applies only to a specific sub-variant, this is stated explicitly. Table 5 summarizes the principal advantages and disadvantages of the individual sub-variants, while the accompanying discussion provides additional context regarding trust distribution, threat mitigation, and practical deployment implications.

4.5.1 | Advantages of Variant 1 – Technician

- The DSO does not need to regenerate passwords from the manufacturer, as all keys and initialization are generated locally.
- Limited manufacturer involvement reduces the DSO's reliance on the manufacturer for security configuration.

TABLE 5 | Key advantages and disadvantages of individual sub-variants.

Variant	Technician			Metrolab			Manufacturer	
	Local	Bridge	Remote	Local	Bridge	Remote	Local	Bridge
	1a	1b	1c	2a	2b	2c	3a	3b
The SM can be deployed immediately upon receipt from the manufacturer.	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓
The SM is capable of encrypted communication immediately after deployment.	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Certificates and keys do not need to be regenerated after deployment.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
HES has a cryptographically supported identity of the SM during initialization, or the identity is guaranteed by local access.	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Low demand on data volume of the primary interface.	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓
Minimal workload for the technician during installation.	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Minimal workload for metrolab staff.	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓
Minimal processing workload for the manufacturer.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗

Note: The data volume comparison reflects relative communication complexity of initialization steps over the primary interface; quantitative traffic measurements were outside the scope of this validation.

- New SMs from the manufacturer can be immediately handed over to technicians for deployment.

4.5.2 | Disadvantages of Variant 1 – Technician

- The HES does not have a cryptographically supported identity of the SM in the initial phase (Variant 1c only).
- The use of one-time roles or one-time passwords may not be correctly implemented by the manufacturer. If a single password is used for all meters, it can potentially be exploited, on the other hand, if each meter is assigned a randomized password during production, there may be issues with securely transferring these passwords from the manufacturer to the distributor.
- The technician must carry out potentially critical installation steps (inserting the SIM card and configuring the PIN).
- The initial setup may take time and require a larger data volume.
- The SM is not capable of secure communication with the HES immediately after being installed at the deployment zone.

4.5.3 | Advantages of Variant 2 – Metrolab

- The technician installs the SM at the deployment zone. No configuration is required, only verification of correct SM communication.

- Critical security operations are performed locally in Metrolab’s secure premises, eliminating the need for random initial passwords (not applicable to Variant 2c).
- The data volume that would otherwise be required for initialization is reduced (not applicable to Variant 2c).
- The SM is capable of secure communication immediately after being installed at the deployment zone.

4.5.4 | Disadvantages of Variant 2 – Metrolab

- The workload of the Metrolab staff may become significantly high.

4.5.5 | Advantages of Variant 3 – Manufacturer

- There is no need for one-time keys or roles.
- The workload of the technician or the Metrolab is eliminated.
- Data transfer from the manufacturer does not require special protection, as it only involves transferring certificates containing the public keys of the SMs (Variant 3a only).

4.5.6 | Disadvantages of Variant 3 – Manufacturer

- A more demanding process for the manufacturer.
- Redundant certificate and key regeneration (Variant 3a only).

- Higher data volumes related to regeneration (Variant 3a only).
- Trust is based on manufacturer-performed steps; the DSO must subsequently regenerate everything (Variant 3a only).
- Requires the establishment of a secure access path from the manufacturer into the DSO infrastructure for HES interaction. This introduces additional integration complexity and temporarily exposes internal DSO systems during initialization (Variant 3b only).

5 | Role-Based Access for Smart Meters

The secure initialization variants presented in Section 4 rely not only on cryptographic mechanisms and certificate provisioning, but also on the correct definition and enforcement of access roles within the smart meter. While the risk analysis in Section 3 identifies threats related to unauthorized access, privilege escalation, and configuration tampering, the practical mitigation of these threats is implemented through role-based access control as defined by the DLMS/COSEM model.

Initialization, normal operation, and long-term security management place fundamentally different requirements on access control. If roles used during deployment are overly permissive, reused during operation, or insufficiently isolated, weaknesses introduced at initialization may persist throughout the meter's lifecycle. Conversely, a well-structured role model allows sensitive initialization steps to be tightly scoped in both time and privilege, and subsequently restricted or disabled once the meter enters operational service.

This section therefore complements the proposed initialization schemes by outlining recommended role separation and privilege allocation for smart meters. The goal is to support secure execution of initialization workflows, enforce least-privilege principles during normal operation, and reduce long-term exposure of security-critical interfaces.

5.1 | Role Separation and Privilege Scope

The secure operation of SMs is closely linked to the use of multiple, clearly separated access roles. Each role should be designed to support a specific operational purpose while minimizing access to unrelated objects. An overview of the recommended roles is shown in Table 6.

The table defines, for each proposed role, the interfaces on which the role should be available, the applicable DLMS authentication mechanism, and the level of message security. Three interface types are considered: an optical interface for local access, a HAN interface for customer access, and a remote interface used for primary communication over the mobile network. Message security is categorized as unencrypted, encrypted, authenticated, or digitally signed (these security levels may be combined).

For frequent and regular meter readings, a dedicated access *reading role* should be used. This role should provide read-only access to measurement-related objects and, where necessary, limited write access to non-critical configuration parameters. Under no

circumstances should this role permit modification of tariff logic, relay control, security settings, or cryptographic material.

Configuration of operationally sensitive parameters, such as tariff tables, relay behavior, or remote disconnection functions, should be performed using a separate *management role*. This role should be used only when configuration changes are required and should not have access to the security settings of other roles, except where explicitly necessary for managing its own authentication material (e.g., to configure technician access). Firmware updates of communication or application logic may also be permitted under this role, provided that updates to certified metrology firmware remain restricted.

Security-critical configuration tasks should be isolated into a dedicated *security management role*. This role is responsible for operations such as updating certificates, modifying authentication credentials, changing security policies, and managing cryptographic keys. Access to this role should require the highest available security level; in the context of DLMS, this implies encrypted communication combined with digitally signed messages. Use of this role should be strictly limited to initialization, re-keying events, or exceptional maintenance scenarios.

For on-site configuration, a local only *technician role* should be used. This role provides limited access to meter configuration and is intended for situations where the remote interface is unavailable and other remote roles cannot access the meter. It may also be used during the initial phase of meter initialization.

Multiple specialized roles may be required for certificate initialization and for updating the root certificate stored in the SM. To simplify the initialization phase, a dedicated *certification role* may be used. This role has unrestricted access to certificate storage objects and is permitted to import or export certificates to and from the SM. It may import only certificates that are part of the PKI, starting with the RootCA. The role may also be used to create the initial certificate for the SM itself (this operation should be permitted only once). After the initialization process is completed, this role should be disabled.

For updating the root certificate, a separate *master certification role* may be defined that is restricted exclusively to this purpose. Although the DLMS standard does not generally assume replacement of the root certificate, such a role becomes relevant if the validity period of the RootCA is shorter than the expected lifetime of the SM, or if cryptographic algorithms must be replaced due to regulatory or technological changes. Given its system-wide impact, access to this role should be tightly controlled and exercised only in exceptional cases. While the root certificate could alternatively be updated as part of a firmware upgrade, this approach may be problematic in practice. It introduces a dependency on the manufacturer and may increase data transfer volume, as some SM firmware architectures do not support differential updates and instead require deployment of a full firmware image.

To complete the set of recommended roles, several additional roles may be defined that are not strictly security-related but are useful or, in some cases, necessary for SM operation. The *public*

TABLE 6 | Role-based access configuration for smart meters.

Role	Interface	Authentication	Encryption	Description
Public	O/R	—	—	Mandatory role required for correct operation of other roles.
Management	O/R	HLS-ECDSA	AE	Configuration and management.
Reading	R	HLS-ECDSA	AE	Read-only access to daily measurement data.
Security management	O/R	HLS-ECDSA	AE + D	Critical role for performing security-sensitive operations.
Technician	O	HLS-SHA-256	E	Basic access for technicians, including SIM and APN setup.
* Certification	O	—	—	Temporary role for certificate import and SM certificate creation.
* Master certification	O/R	HLS-ECDSA	AE + D	Additional role for root certificate update.
HAN	H	HLS-SHA-256	E	Basic role for customer access. Read only access.
Push	R	—	AE	Role for setting up encryption keys for secured push messages.
* Unsecured push	R	—	—	Public push messages without encryption.

*Roles marked in this way are not strictly necessary, but they may facilitate the initial initialization process or extend the available configuration options.

O = optical interface, R = remote interface (primary interface, e.g., mobile network), H = HAN interface (customer local interface);

A = authenticated messages, E = encrypted messages, D = digitally signed messages.

role provides basic access to meter information and is required for encrypted roles, as it enables reading of role invocation counters. The *HAN* role is intended for customer access and may be configured for one-way or two-way communication; in current Czech deployments, DSOs use periodic push messaging only. The *push* role specifies security keys for one-way encrypted messages sent by the meter to the HES (e.g., alarms or events). Optionally, an *unsecured push* role may be defined for unencrypted push messaging where minimal latency is required, such as last-gasp messages transmitted during loss of power.

6 | Verification with DSO

In cooperation with multiple DSOs, the proposed initialization variants were verified through cybersecurity testing on real SMs and controlled validation using dedicated tools. The verification activities focused on confirming that the proposed schemes are feasible in operational DSO environments and can be implemented using standardized DLMS mechanisms without deviations from the specification.

The verification was performed as part of ongoing cybersecurity testing of SMs prior to field deployment [33] (in our smart grid laboratory Figure 6). While complete end-to-end initialization workflows were not executed on production systems, selected security-critical procedures were validated on real smart meters and operational head-end Systems. The primary objectives of the verification were derived from the deployment aspects defined at the beginning of Section 4, the dominant threat categories identified in Section 3, and established practices from cybersecurity testing of real smart meters conducted prior to their deployment in operational DSO environments. Accordingly, the verification focused on confirming that:

FIGURE 6 | Smart grid laboratory.

- the proposed initialization variants are compatible with standard DLMS objects and procedures,
- cryptographic material (keys and certificates) can be securely provisioned, updated, and replaced on real devices,
- initialization-related procedures align with established DSO operational processes,
- selected threats identified in the STRIDE-based analysis are effectively mitigated by the proposed security mechanisms.

To support these activities, several dedicated tools were developed and used. These include a DLMS client application [43] and a DLMS server application [44], both designed to support fine-grained control over authentication, certificate handling, role

configuration, and key management. These tools were used to validate initialization workflows and systematically test individual security procedures.

The verification covered selected sub-variants of all three proposed initialization approaches (technician, metrolab, and manufacturer). On real smart meters, the tests focused on cybersecurity-relevant procedures that are directly applicable in operational environments, including:

- certificate provisioning and validation against the DSO RootCA,
- generation and update of cryptographic keys,
- execution of certificate-based authentication using HLS-ECDSA,
- updating security algorithms and cryptographic parameters,
- usability of the proposed schemes in the DSO infrastructure.

Complete initialization schemes, including variant specific step sequences and trust-domain transitions, were validated using the developed DLMS tools. This enabled repeatable testing of initialization logic and role transitions without affecting operational systems.

The verification confirmed that the proposed initialization variants rely exclusively on standardized DLMS security suites and role-based access control mechanisms, without requiring proprietary extensions or non-standard procedures. The results demonstrate that cryptographic material can be securely updated after deployment, thereby supporting long-term maintainability and cryptographic agility in operational AMI systems. The objective of the verification was not to provide statistical performance benchmarks or exhaustive penetration testing, but to demonstrate technical feasibility, standards compliance, and correct enforcement of security controls in realistic DSO environments. Performance evaluation and resilience testing under adversarial conditions are therefore considered complementary directions for future work.

In collaboration with a DSO, we developed a Smartbox [45] used for testing and validation of a wide range of scenarios, which can also support real-world verification. The Smartbox is part of a larger integrated validation environment (Figure 7), which enables practical validation of selected workflows and communication scenarios.

As part of this cooperation, large-scale validation was performed using a DLMS server emulator deployed as a virtual machine (VM) within the DSO infrastructure. Each VM instance supports up to 50,000 simulated smart meters⁸. Higher device counts can be achieved through horizontal scaling by deploying multiple VM instances. The emulator is routinely used prior to SM roll-out to verify HES operation and cybersecurity controls under realistic load conditions. It should be emphasized that this large-scale setup was not used to benchmark the proposed initialization procedures across tens of thousands of devices. Instead, it served to verify interoperability with the DSO backend, validate communication handling at scale, and confirm correct enforcement of security policies within a realistically dimensioned infrastructure.

FIGURE 7 | Smart grid Demonstrator with Smartbox.

The emulated meters implemented only the DLMS objects required for the evaluated scenarios, enabling scalable testing of communication patterns, backend integration, and HES behavior under load. Pseudo-random consumption data were generated to approximate operational traffic; a subset of this dataset is published in [46].

7 | Summary

This article addressed a critical insufficiently specified aspect of smart metering systems: the secure deployment and initialization of smart meters prior to their first authenticated operational communication. While DLMS provides mechanisms for secure data exchange during operation, the establishment of trust anchors, cryptographic identities, and roles during deployment remains a practical challenge for DSOs.

To close this gap, the paper first established a comprehensive security context by combining regulatory requirements, DLMS security mechanisms, and a structured STRIDE-based threat analysis. The resulting security diagram and data flow analysis highlighted initialization as a long-term trust boundary, where weaknesses may persist throughout the meter's operational lifetime if not properly addressed.

Based on these findings, three initialization variants were proposed and analyzed: technician-based initialization at the deployment zone, initialization in a secure DSO lab, and manufacturer-based initialization. Each variant was further decomposed into

sub-variants reflecting different communication paths and trust distributions and evaluated with respect to cybersecurity assurance, operational feasibility, workload distribution, and handling of sensitive cryptographic material.

The comparison showed that no single approach is universally optimal. Technician-based initialization minimizes manufacturer trust but increases field complexity and exposure, particularly when remote initialization over unsecured channels is used. Metrolab-based initialization offers a balanced compromise by centralizing sensitive operations in a controlled environment while reducing field workload. Manufacturer-based initialization enables immediate secure deployment and minimizes operational effort for the DSO, but shifts trust and complexity toward the manufacturer and, in some sub-variants, requires subsequent regeneration of cryptographic material.

Finally, the feasibility of the proposed schemes was validated through cooperation with DSOs using dedicated DLMS testing tools and large-scale emulation environments. These activities confirmed that all proposed variants can be implemented using standardized DLMS mechanisms without deviations from the specification, while remaining compatible with current regulatory and cybersecurity expectations.

8 | Discussion

The results of this work show that secure SM initialization is a security-critical operational process spanning multiple organizational domains, including manufacturing, laboratory testing, and field deployment. Decisions made at this stage directly influence long-term properties such as device identity, key management, auditability, and cryptographic agility.

A central finding is the unavoidable trade-off between trust distribution and operational efficiency. Variants that minimize trust in the manufacturer increase complexity and risk during installation, whereas variants that prioritize operational efficiency require stronger contractual, procedural, and technical assurances within the supply chain. This observation aligns with regulatory expectations emphasizing verifiable and auditable initialization procedures.

The analysis further demonstrates that local or bridged initialization mechanisms provide significantly stronger security guarantees than early remote initialization via the primary communication interface. Approaches relying on unsecured remote communication expose the system to spoofing and identity uncertainty before a cryptographically verifiable device identity is established.

The proposed schemes also highlight the importance of strict role-based access control within the smart meter. Separation of operational, management, and security roles is essential to enforcing least-privilege principles throughout the device lifetime and should be considered an integral part of any secure deployment strategy.

From a forward-looking perspective, the proposed schemes also support cryptographic agility. By anchoring trust in a well-

defined PKI hierarchy and avoiding hard-coded symmetric master keys, the initialization approaches facilitate future transitions toward stronger algorithms, including post-quantum cryptography (PQC) [42]. This is particularly relevant given the long service life of smart meters and the evolving regulatory emphasis on future-proof security controls.

In cases where a smart meter does not provide sufficient computational capacity to apply PQC to every message or connection, PQC algorithms can instead be used for periodic updates of the key-encryption key via a post-quantum key-agreement mechanism. As this operation is performed infrequently, strict latency requirements do not apply.

Overall, this work demonstrates that secure smart meter deployment can be standardized without extending or modifying the DLMS specification. By treating initialization as a first-class security process and offering multiple validated deployment variants, the article provides DSOs with a practical framework adaptable to different operational models, regulatory environments, and risk profiles.

9 | Future Work

Building on the security implications and design trade-offs discussed in the previous section, future work will focus on refining the proposed initialization schemes toward a small set of well-defined reference implementations. In particular, one or two gold-standard initialization approaches will be selected and fully specified, including detailed operational workflows, role definitions, cryptographic procedures, and error-handling mechanisms. These reference schemes will be validated through real-world implementations and tested in cooperation with DSOs to assess their practicality, robustness, and operational overhead.

Further development will concentrate on extending the existing DLMS testing tools and smart meter emulation environment to support complete end-to-end initialization workflows, including realistic consumption data generation. This will enable repeatable validation of certificate provisioning, role lifecycle management, secure channel establishment, and transitions from deployment to normal operation.

Future work will also examine the applicability of post-quantum cryptography on smart meters with constrained computational and memory resources. Rather than assuming universal deployment of PQC, the focus will be on evaluating conservative integration strategies within the proposed schemes, such as hybrid approaches where post-quantum algorithms are used selectively for infrequent operations, including key-encryption key updates or certificate renewal, while classical cryptography is retained for routine communication.

In addition, the refined schemes will be analyzed to identify potential operational bottlenecks, including PKI scalability limits, initialization throughput during mass deployment, and dependencies on manufacturer or laboratory infrastructure. Based on these analyses, recommended practices for key and certificate rotation will be specified, taking into account device lifetime,

regulatory requirements, cryptographic transition planning, and operational cost.

Author Contributions

David Kohout: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, resources, software, visualization, writing – original draft. **Tomas Lieskován:** formal analysis, methodology, resources, validation. **Dr. Petr Mlynek:** funding acquisition, project administration, supervision, writing – review & editing. **Radek Fujdiak:** formal analysis, supervision. **Jason Jaskolka:** formal analysis, writing – review & editing.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The pseudo-random consumption data that support part of the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18195581>. Other data generated or analyzed during the study were produced within operational environments and are not publicly available due to security and confidentiality constraints.

Endnotes

- ¹APN (access point name): a private cellular access point used in smart metering to terminate meter data sessions into a non-public packet data network, enforcing dedicated routing, isolation, and security policies. It provides VPN-like separation by keeping metering traffic off the public internet and routing it directly to the utility’s backend systems.
- ²For the higher security setup, the number of certificates for the HES depends on the number of access roles defined on the SM.
- ³Local access can be provided via an optical interface, RS-485, or other interface.
- ⁴The device used for this process is typically capable of performing most required configuration steps automatically. It may be a laptop or a tablet and can also be used by metrolab technicians in Variant 2.
- ⁵Ideally, this is a technician role that relies on an authentication password generated on the SM by the manufacturer. As part of secure initialization, it is recommended that such passwords be regenerated during the process.
- ⁶Alternatively, the MMD SubCA may be signed by the HES SubCA.
- ⁷In theory, if the meter already contains all required certificates, neither a shipment file nor a secure transfer channel is strictly necessary.
- ⁸The practical limit per instance is determined primarily by available TCP ports and resource allocation. For scalability and system compatibility reasons, the first 10,000 ports are not used due to reserved and registered services.

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